

A Novel Flavonol Glycoside : 4'-Methoxykaempferol-3-O- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl-7-O- β -D-xylopyranoside from the Leaves of *Cassia biflora*

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The genus *Cassia* (Leguminosae, Subfamily Caeseliaceae) comprises about 580 species distributed mostly in the tropical and subtropical region of the world¹. About 20 species found in India are extensively used in the folk medicine for the treatment of cheloid tumors, ring worm, insect-bites and rheumatism². Recently, we have reported a new flavonol glycoside, kaempferol-7-O- β -D-galactopyranosyl(1 \rightarrow 4)- α -L-rhamnopyranoside along with known flavonol glycosides, quercetin-3-O- β -D-glucopyranoside and myricetin-3-O- α -L-rhamnopyranoside from the leaves of this plant³. In the present paper, we report the isolation of a novel flavonol glycoside, 4'-methoxykaempferol-3-O- α -L-rhamnopyranoside-7-O- β -D-xylopyranoside (**1**) from the leaves of *Cassia biflora*.

Results and Discussion

The ethyl acetate soluble portion of the dried methanolic extract of the leaves of *C. biflora* on cc over Si-gel (B.D.H.) and elution with ethyl acetate-acetone yielded a pale yellow coloured crystalline solid, m.p. 277–78 $^{\circ}$, C₂₇H₃₀O₁₄. It responded to all positive tests of flavonol glycoside⁴. Uv spectral data with diagnostic shift reagents^{5,6} suggest that **1** is a 3,7,4'-trisubstituted-flavonol glycoside. On hydrolysis with 2N HCl, **1** gave an equimolar mixture of L-rhamnose, D-xylose (pc and glc) and an aglycone (**2**), m.p. 229 $^{\circ}$, which was characterised as 4'-methoxykaempferol by its spectral studies. ¹H nmr spectrum of the acetate derivative of **1** exhibited two *ortho*-coupled

doublets at δ 8.10 and 7.45 (*J* 8.5 Hz) which corresponded A₂B₂ pattern of B-ring. Two meta-coupled doublets at δ 7.17 and 6.85 (*J* 2.5 Hz) were attributed to C-8 and C-6 protons respectively. Two sharp singlets at δ 2.46 and 3.85 each for three protons, were assigned to OAc-5 and OCH₃-4'. The anomeric protons at δ 5.17 (*J* 9.0 Hz) and 5.57 (*J* 1.2 Hz) were assigned to H-1 xylose (β -configuration) and H-1 rhamnose (α -configuration) respectively. ¹³C nmr spectrum of **1** revealed the presence of 27 carbon atoms in the molecule which was comparable with the related structure. The mass spectrum of the acetate of **1** showed a fragment ion of *m/z* 342, which corresponded to the loss of both acetylated sugar moieties. The aglycone fragment was observed at *m/z* 300. A retro-Diels-Alder fragmentation pattern was observed at *m/z* 153 and 135, showing the presence of two OH-groups in ring-A and one OCH₃ group in ring-B.

Enzymatic hydrolysis of **1** with β -xylosidase (Sigma) gave D-xylose and a partial glycoside (**3**). Methylation of **3** followed by hydrolysis gave a partial methyl ether (**4**), m.p. 135–36 $^{\circ}$, characterised as 3-OH, 5,7,4'-trimethoxykaempferol by spectral and chromatographic comparison with authentic sample⁷. The methylated sugar was identified as 2,3,4-tri-O-methyl-L-rhamnose by tlc according to Petek⁸. This finally established that L-rhamnose was α -linked at C-3 while D-xylose was β -linked at C-7 position. Quantitative estimation of sugars⁹ indicated the presence of two moles of sugar/mole of aglycone.

On the basis of the above results, compound **1** has been identified as 4'-methoxykaempferol-3-O- α -L-rhamnopyranoside-7-O- β -D-xylopyranoside.

1 : R = H
1a : R = AC

2 : R¹, R², R³ = H
3 : R¹, R² = H, R³ = rham
4 : R¹, R² = CH₃, R³ = OH

Experimental

Melting points were determined on a Reichert microscope hot-stage apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were taken on a Shimadzu IR-408 spectrometer, mass spectra on a Jeol JMS-300 spectrometer, ¹H nmr spectra on a JEOL-GX (270 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal standard and ¹³C nmr (DMSO-d₆) on a FT instrument (50 MHz).

Air-dried and powdered leaves of *C. biflora* were extracted with petroleum-ether (b.p. 40–60°) and the residue was extracted with MeOH (B.D.H.). The MeOH solution was concentrated and hot H₂O added to the residue. After cooling, it was successively extracted with Et₂O, EtOAc and n-BuOH. The EtOAc fraction was subjected to column chromatography over Si-gel and eluted with EtOAc-acetone (3 : 2) to get compound **1**

as pale yellow granules, m.p. 277–78° (Found : C, 56.55; H, 5.19, C₂₇H₃₀O₁₅ calcd. for : C, 56.51; H 5.15%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 465 (OH), 1 675 (C=O), 1 620 (C=C aromatic), 2 950 (C-H) and 1 110–1 020 cm⁻¹ (O-gly); λ_{\max} (MeOH) 240sh, 260, 309sh, 360, (+AlCl₃), 244sh, 275, 306sh, 408, (+AlCl₃-HCl), 267, 290sh, 356, 402, (+NaOMe), 245sh, 262, 380, (+NaOAc), 262, 318sh, 362, 396 nm.

Acetylation of 1 : Compound **1** on acetylation with Ac₂O/Py (1 : 2, 48 h, at 25° room temperature) and on usual work-up afforded a heptacetate derivative (**1a**), C₄₁H₄₄O₂₁, m.p. 142–43°; ¹H nmr δ (270 MHz; CDCl₃) 6.85 (1H, d, *J* 2.5 Hz, H-6), 7.17 (1H, d, *J* 2.5 Hz, H-8), 7.45 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, H-3',5'), 8.10 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, H-2',6'), 5.17 (1H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz, H-1 xylose), 5.57 (1H, d, *J* 1.2 Hz, H-1 rham), 1.25 (3H, d, *J* 6.2 Hz, rham-CH₃), 3.85 (3H, s, OCH₃-4'), 3.67–5.60 (11H, m, gly-H), 2.46 (3H, s, OAc-5) and 1.95–2.20 (18H, m, aliphatic MeCO); ¹³C nmr of **1** δ (50 MHz; DMSO-d₆) 156.2 (C-2), 133.8 (C-3), 177.9 (C-4), 161.0 (C-5), 99.1 (C-6), 161.9 (C-7), 94.5 (C-8), 156.7 (C-9), 102.5 (C-10), 121.7 (C-1'), 130.5 (C-2',6'), 116.0 (C-3',5'), 159.8 (C-4'), 103.1 (C-1''), 70.3 (C-2''), 70.7 (C-3''), 71.6 (C-4''), 71.7 (C-5''), 17.8 (C-6''), 101.8 (C-1'''), 78.2 (C-2'''), 77.3 (C-3'''), 84.1 (C-4'''), 61.8 (C-5'''), 55.7 (OMe); EIMS (70 eV) *m/z* 614 [*M*-acetylatedpentose + H]⁺, 600 [*M*-acetylated hexose + H]⁺, 342 [*M*-acetylated sugars + 2H]⁺, 300 [aglycone]⁺, 273 [(rham)Ac₃]⁺, 259 [(xyl)Ac₃]⁺, 153 [A₁ + H]⁺ and 135 [B₂]⁺.

Acid hydrolysis of 1 : The glycoside **1** was refluxed with 2N HCl-MeOH (5 ml) for 2 h at 100°. Water was then added and the mixture was extracted with EtOAc. The EtOAc fraction which contained aglycone, was crystallised from CHCl₃-MeOH as yellow needles (**2**), m.p. 229–30°. The aglycone (**2**) was identified as 4'-methoxykaempferol (Found : C, 64.02; H, 4.04. C₁₆H₁₂O₆ calcd. for : C, 64.00; H, 4.00%).

The aqueous hydrolysate after neutralisation with Ag₂CO₃ was subjected to pc using butanol-

acetic acid-water (4 : 1 : 2) and butanol-water-EtOH (4 : 1 : 5) with authentic sugars as checks. The R_f values of the sugars were identical with those of rhamnose (0.37, 0.28) and xylose (0.17, 0.15).

Glc of sugars : The neutral aqueous hydrolysate was evaporated to dryness and dissolved in pyridine (5 ml), trimethyl chlorosilazane (1 ml) and hexamethyl disilazane (1 ml). The mixture was separated on a column of 2% OV-1 silinised chromosorb W at 185° using N₂ flow rate of 50 ml/min. The R_t (min) values observed for the TMSi ether derivatives investigated corresponded to α - and β -rhamnose (3.9, 3.8) and α - and β -xylose (3.9, 4.5 min). The observed R_t values were in agreement with those of rhamnose and xylose.

Enzymatic hydrolysis of 1 : A mixture of compound 1 (75 mg) and β -xylosidase (10 mg) were incubated in (NH₄)₂SO₄-NaOAc buffer (pH 5.0) at 25° for 30 h and then after addition of water it was extracted with n-BuOH. The n-BuOH extract was chromatographed over silica gel column to give a partial glycoside (3), m.p. 165–67°, which was identified as 4'-methoxykaempferol-3-O-rhamnoside by its spectral studies. From the water layer, D-xylose was identified by pc (four solvents).

Permethylation of 3 followed by acid hydrolysis : CH₃I (1 ml) and Ag₂O (30 mg) were added to a solution of 3 (20 mg) in DMF (5 ml). The mixture was stirred in dark at room temperature for 48 h. The contents were filtered and the residue was treated with ethanol (25 ml). The syrupy residue was hydrolysed with 2N HCl. After usual work up it gave 3-OH,

5,7,4'-trimethoxyflavone (4), m.p.135–36° (Found : C, 65.96; H, 4.98. Calcd. : C, 65.85; H, 4.87%). The methylated sugars were identified as 2,3,4-tri-O-methyl-L-rhamnose, $[\alpha]_D + 26$ (in H₂O), 2,3,4-tri-O-methyl-D-xylose, $[\alpha]_D 4.3^\circ$ (in MeOH), separated by preparative tlc on silica gel (toluene-MeOH, 4 : 1).

Quantitative estimation of sugars : The anhydrous glycoside (25 mg) was hydrolysed with 0.2 N HCl. After cooling overnight, the aglycone was filtered, dried and weighed (11.0 mg). The ratio of aglycone to glycoside is 44.0% indicating the presence of two moles of sugar/mole of aglycone.

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